

Conference Abstract

Is there any chance in a three-front war? The past, present and possible future of muddy water fish species in Hungarian waters

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Received: 15 Dec 2025 | Published: 30 Dec 2025

Citation: Weiperth A, Bányai MZ, Berényi DA, Bláha M, Kouba A, Müller T (2025) Is there any chance in a three-front war? The past, present and possible future of muddy water fish species in Hungarian waters.

ARPHA Conference Abstracts 8: e182563. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.8.e182563>

Abstract

In this presentation we focus on key aspects that have affected wetland fish species in the past and affect them presently, as well as new challenges they are likely to face in the future. Numerous factors have influenced the fish fauna of the Carpathian Basin over the centuries. The first major changes were caused by river regulation, which began in the early 18th century. This was followed by the introduction of non-native species through both illegal and legal stocking and their natural spread. Finally, increasingly rapid climate change has begun to cause ever greater problems. Due to the combined effects of these three processes, muddy water fish populations are now on the edge of extinction. Here, we demonstrate how current maintenance practices are destroying the remaining populations of weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*) in the lowland stream and channel network systems. Additionally, the co-occurrence of invasive marbled crayfish (*Procambarus virginalis*) and several invasive fish species (e.g. Chinese sleeper

Percottus glenii, Jaguar guapote *Parachromis managuensis*, Eastern mosquitofish *Gambusia holbrooki*) has affected the population of the European mudminnow (*Umbra krameri*) in the western drainage region of Lake Balaton. We emphasise the challenge posed by non-native species, which will require sustained management in the future, as well as changes in water management practices and angling stocking programs. Education programmes targeting all age groups, from children to adults, are also required. All of these measures are urgently needed to ensure the preservation of muddy-water fish species in Hungarian waters.

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Presented at

International Conference "The Fish of Muddy Waters"

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.